

Fitting of data: JBW-NP-P-V3 2021-02-18_09-05-17
 $0.0184 \leq q \text{ (nm}^{-1}\text{)} \leq 25.1$
Active parameters: 1, ranges: 1
Background level: 0.0237 ± 0.000996
(Scaling factor: $2.89\text{e}+33 \pm 2.27\text{e}+31$)
Timing: 10 repetitions of 48.9 ± 1.61 seconds

Range $1.500\text{e}-10$ to $1.500\text{e}-07$, vol-weighted
totalValue: $1.992\text{e}-04 \pm 6.288\text{e}-07$
mean: $3.344\text{e}-09 \pm 4.107\text{e}-12$
variance: $6.525\text{e}-19 \pm 4.162\text{e}-20$
skew: $2.583\text{e}-01 \pm 4.199\text{e}-01$
kurtosis: $6.389\text{e}+00 \pm 2.091\text{e}+00$

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